

The Development Of Solar Charger Based On Sun Detector Using Arduino

(Pembangunan Pengecas Solar Berasaskan Pengesanan Suria Menggunakan Arduino)

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ABSTRACT

Green energy, often known as renewable energy, has recently received a lot of attention. Solar energy, hydro potential energy, wind energy, biomass energy, and terrestrial heat are examples of renewable energy sources. Solar energy is one of these that is both effective and practical. Solar panels are very popular nowadays, and they are frequently used to convert solar energy into electricity. The majority of solar panels on the market and in use today are static, meaning they cannot create more power. To gather more sunlight, the solar panel should always be parallel to the sun. Using solar panel tracking, this technology seeks to generate more power from sunlight. The power generated by the solar panels will be at their peak if they are parallel to the sun. In other words, the location of the solar panel is the focus of this project. Hardware, electrical, and software development are all part of this system. The microcontroller is then connected to the motor servo and sensor circuit. Finally, write a programme to operate the sensor and servo motor, and upload it to Arduino. The purpose of this project is to create a system that automatically tracks the position of the sun. The device will adjust the angle of the solar panels to maintain them parallel to the sun at all times, generating maximum power. A single-axis sun detector device is provided in this project, and its effectiveness is tested. Finally, the solar panel on this system can be changed to follow the sun's movement and might even charge electronic devices such as smartphones.

Keywords: Solar Panel; Motor Servo; Sensor; Single Axis Solar Detector; Telephone

ABSTRAK

Tenaga yang boleh diperbaharui yang terkategori sebagai tenaga hijau telah mendapat banyak perhatian pada masa kini. Antara jenis tenaga yang boleh diperbaharui adalah tenaga solar, tenaga keupayaan hidro, tenaga angin, tenaga biojisim dan haba daratan. Antara tenaga yang paling mendapat sambutan di Malaysia adalah tenaga solar. Pada masa kini, panel solar adalah yang popular dan sering digunakan untuk menukar tenaga solar kepada tenaga elektrik. Kebanyakan panel solar yang wujud dan digunakan sekarang adalah statik, kesannya ia tidak boleh menjana kuasa yang lebih maksimum. Dalam usaha untuk mendapatkan lebih banyak tenaga, kedudukan panel solar perlu sentiasa selari dengan matahari. Objektif utama bagi projek ini adalah untuk menjana lebih banyak kuasa daripada cahaya matahari dengan menggunakan panel penjejak matahari. Jika panel solar selari dengan matahari, kuasa yang dijana daripada panel solar akan menjadi maksimum. Sistem ini terdiri daripada pembangunan perkakasan, elektrik dan perisian. Perintang bergantung cahaya telah digunakan sebagai sensor untuk mengesan cahaya matahari. Kemudian, motor servo dan litar sensor disambungkan dengan pengawal mikro. Seterusnya, membangunkan satu program untuk mengawal sensor dan stepper motor dan memasukkan program pada Arduino. Matlamat projek ini adalah untuk membangunkan satu sistem pengesanan kedudukan matahari secara automatik. Sistem ini akan menggerakkan panel solar supaya selari dengan matahari dan menjana kuasa yang maksimum pada setiap masa. Dalam projek ini, peranti pengesanan solar satu paksi dibentangkan dan telah diuji keberkesannya. Akhir sekali, solar panel pada sistem ini dapat diselaraskan mengikut pergerakan matahari dan mampu untuk mengecas peranti elektronik seperti telefon.

Kata Kunci: Panel Solar; Motor Servo; Pengesanan; Panel Pengesanan Matahari Satu Paksi; Telefon

INTRODUCTION

Demand for electricity generation is increasing over time. The total average amount of electricity generation in 2018 is 20261 TeraWatt hours per year. Energy sources include coal, natural gas, oil, biomass, nuclear energy and renewable energy such as solar energy, hydropower and geothermal energy. Among renewable energy, solar energy is a clean and renewable energy source. Solar energy is

the best way to reduce its carbon footprint and it does not cause environmental pollution. Not only that, this renewable energy does not release any greenhouse gases. It only needs a light source to function. Therefore, it is safe and environmentally friendly. However, there are still many people, especially in Malaysia, who still doubt why solar energy is good.

FIGURE 1. Annual radiation rate in Malaysia.

Figure 1 shows the average annual rate received by each area in Malaysia. Almost 98 percent of the states in Malaysia get a high value rate while 2 percent get a moderate value. Sunlight consists of two components namely “direct rays” which carry about 90 percent of solar energy and “diffuse sunlight.” Since most of the energy is in direct radiation, maximum accumulation requires the sun to be visible by the panel for as long as possible. On more cloudy days, the ratio of direct and diffused light can drop as low as 60:40 or lower.

Problem Statement

Malaysia is one of the countries that use energy resources from petroleum and natural gas. Based on statistics released by Tenaga Nasional Berhad, a total of 685 million kilowatts of energy were supplied to homes in 2016. However, there was an increase of 31 percent to 900 million kilowatts in 2019. This change in data shows that the demand for electricity supply is very high in Malaysia from time to time. Based on non-renewable resources as the main source of power generation, Malaysia will experience the problem of depletion of natural resources in the long run.

With a high average annual radiation rate, Malaysia has the potential to become a country that uses solar energy as a source of power. Today, the use of solar systems is very widespread among Malaysians either for personal use or facilities provided by the government itself. The use of static type solar systems has become a major choice among consumers. This type of static solar system only points in one direction according to the suitability of the place and the highest average rate of radiation produced by the sun. With this static position of the solar panel it cannot take advantage of all the radiation produced by the sun as the earth rotates on its axis.

There are several types of solar energy available and can be used including solar thermal technology, passive solar extraction and photovoltaic type solar. All these types of solar energy have the same function which is to capture sunlight to produce electricity in different ways. The selection of the photovoltaic type solar system is the most suitable for use in Malaysia because photovoltaic type solar has the highest efficiency in accordance with the weather in Malaysia compared to other solar systems.

Literature Review

Solar tracker type systems produce more electrical energy than static type solar systems. This is because the radiation emitted by the sun is exposed directly parallel to the surface of the solar board. In addition, the amount of space required by a solar tracking system is equal to the amount of surface required to build a fixed type solar system making it ideal for optimizing the amount of land surface to be used. Technological advances and the reliability of electronic and mechanical components make this system durable for a long period of time while reducing concerns about ongoing maintenance over time. (Pratik Pawar, Ashish Yadav, Pritam Makwana 2018)

Although solar energy is a good source of energy, there are some improvements made to obtain maximum results in utilizing solar energy. Among the improvements made is by using a solar tracking system instead of a fixed system. Introduction of the idea of developing a single axis solar solar tracker for solar panels. The circuit is controlled by an Atmega328P microcontroller, two dependent resistors (LDR) and a servo motor. The purpose of the research was to see a comparison of the output voltage readings for fixed type panels and solar tracker type. (Jumaat et al. 2018)

METHODOLOGY

Experiment Design and Procedure

The system consists of 3 main parts namely input, main controller and output. The inputs are for sensors and power supply while the outputs are included with servo motors and solar panels.

FIGURE 2. Hardware configuration

Figure 2 above describes the overall arrangement of the components and how the system

works. The microcontroller is used as the main key of the controller to control all parts of the system. The Arduino Uno is used to process data input and output and control the solar tracking system. It is also used because of its suitability for small systems and easy to program. In addition, the Arduino Uno can also control many types of sensors, especially servo motors. For the input part, a light dependent resistor (LDR) is connected to the main controller, the Arduino Uno. LDR is used because it can detect sunlight and provide data to the microcontroller for processing. The LDR functions as a sunlight detector and it indicates the direction of sunlight by comparing the intensity of received sunlight. For system output, servo motors have been used to move the solar platform. It will receive the processed data from the microcontroller and move as programmed. Its movement is in the direction of sunlight received by the Light Dependent Resistor. After that, the solar panel will receive and transform the light into electricity as shown below.

FIGURE 3. Solar charge control circuit.

Figure 3 above shows the connection of the battery as well as the components needed to produce 5V output. In this project, the battery used is a Lithium-ion type battery with a capacity value of 2000 mAh. While the output is 3.7V in direct current. A push switch is installed to turn the circuit on and off. At the end of the circuit, a voltage booster with a USB type A connection is used to boost the voltage up to 5V output voltage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation

The simulation of the solar detector circuit is done in matlab simulink application. This simulation involves the movement of the sun as well as solar panels. Figure 4 shows the arrangement of components and circuits for a solar panel of a solar detector.

FIGURE 4. Circuit simulation using matlab

FIGURE 5. Output simulation

Figure 5 above shows the position of the sun and solar panels. X-axis is time while, y-axis stand for displacement. The red color signal indicates the position of the sun while the blue color signal indicates the position of the solar panel. This simulation test is performed in the matlab simulink application. While the data for the position of the sun is also taken from the matlab source which contains the movement of data for the sun in real situations. The data for this sun explains that the sun will be in the east in the morning and slowly move west in the evening. In the diagram above the x-axis refers to a predetermined time in a clock, while the y-axis refers to the position of the solar and solar panels.

Prototype

Because of its solid structure and ease of nailing or screwing, hard wood is the best choice for prototyping and building the frame. But before the framework is made, measurements and sketches should be done first to ensure the project runs as planned. In addition, the project dimensions should include all electronic components used in the project such as battery, solar panel, arduino uno and servo motor.

FIGURE 6. Arrangement of components

Figure 6 describes the connection and assembly of components into a prototype. Testing on the applicability of all components to the prototype is done to prove the effectiveness of simulation tests that have been done previously can be practical. The solar panel is placed on the surface of the prototype

while the position of the two LDRs is between the two corners of the left and right solar panel. All other components such as the arduino, battery and voltage booster module are placed in the center of the prototype.

The connection made between the solar panel and the servo motor. The wire is tied to a hole found on the blade of the servo motor which is then connected and glued to the bottom surface of the solar panel. Overall, both ends of the motor blade are fastened and connected to the left and right surface

of the solar panel. This will cause every movement made by the servo motor will also move the solar panel in parallel with its movement. Ultimately, the LDR will find the signal where the position of the highest light intensity is parallel to the position of the sun and then send the signal to the arduino for processing. The Arduino will collect and send a signal to the servo motor to perform the motion. The slight movement performed by the servo motor also results in the movement of the solar panel to move parallel to the position of the sun's rays.

FIGURE 7. Measurement of output voltage on solar panel.

TABLE 1. Output voltage for solar panel.

Number of trials	Output voltage(V)
1	3.01
2	3.83
3	2.91
4	0.71
5	1.61
6	3.35
7	2.73
8	2.05
9	3.48
10	3.50

Figure 7 above shows the method of measurement that has been done. Measurements are performed using a digital multimeter that has been set to dc voltage measuring mode. All measurement data are shown in table 1. A total of ten measurement experiments were performed to identify the characteristics of the output voltage. As shown the highest output voltage from the solar panel is 3.83V and the lowest is 0.71V.

Next, measurements of current and voltage were performed on the voltage booster module. This measurement is important to make sure the current and voltage values are the same as other chargers out there. The current and voltage values should be 5mA and 5V dc respectively. This is a fixed value for charging all devices that use usb type A. In figure 8 below shows the measurement method and output values for current and voltage.

FIGURE 8. Measurement of current and voltage values.

FIGURE 9. Final result.

Figure 9 above shows the testing of a sun tracker solar panel. The position of the solar panel moves according to the light emitted by the phone which acts as radiation from the sun. Both light-dependent resistors work as planned. The resistor responds to changes in light intensity that occur between the resistors. Then the motor moves the solar panel from 45 degrees to 145 degrees. Finally testing the effectiveness of phone charging was carried out.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a solar charger system based on solar detectors using arduino has been developed. A system using photovoltaic solar panels is used in this project to capture and convert light into electrical energy. Later, the use of lithium-ion batteries as an energy storage field. Next, the effectiveness of solar panel solar trackers has been tested for effectiveness.

Finally, the system is capable of charging phones and other devices such as power banks.

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